

Optical Properties and Molecular Weight of Silicic Acid during the Course of its Polymerisation

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Silicic acid, prepared by passing sodium silicate solution through H-ion exchange resin, undergoes condensation polymerisation and the reaction is of the third order. The changes in the optical properties, viz., dissymmetry, depolarisation, and turbidity, during polymerisation have been studied by measuring the intensity of scattered light at different angles. The shape of the particles has been found to be spherical. The average molecular weight of the particles at different stages of polymerisation has been determined from measurement of light scattering and viscosity.

The changes in the optical properties of silicic acid during polymerisation have been studied to some extent by Subramiah¹ and Prasad and Guruswamy². Nauman and Debye³ have measured casually the turbidity and molecular weight of a silicic acid sol at a stable state of polymerisation, using the light-scattering technique. Polymerisation kinetics, based on the change in turbidity and particle size, have been reported by Greenburg and Sinclair⁴. Audsely and Aveston⁵ have followed the polymerisation of silicic acid molecules by the determination of molecular weight. Except Audsely and Aveston, all other authors have used sols prepared by adding an acid to a silicate solution. These sols were therefore impure. We have, however, used in our experiments pure silicic acid solution, obtained by the ion-exchange method. The molecular weight of the particles at various stages of polymerisation has been studied by light scattering and viscosity measurements.

EXPERIMENTAL

The reagents used were sodium metasilicate of A.R. quality and Amberlite IR-120(H), a strong cation-exchange resin of Rohm & Haas Company, Pennsylvania.

A Brice Phoenix Universal Light Scattering Spectrophotometer and a Differential Refractometer of the same Company were used. The standardisation of these instruments was previously checked by using solutions of known turbidity.

Preparation of the Silicic Acid.—A known quantity of the aforesaid resin was taken in a tall pyrex glass column on a glass wool bed and washed repeatedly with conductivity water. A solution of sodium silicate in double distilled water, previously filtered through Whatman No. 42 paper and sintered glass filter of pore size 15 microns, was then percolated

1. *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1935, 1A, 709.
2. *Ibid.*, 1944, 19A, 47.
3. *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1953, 57, 1.
4. *Ibid.*, 1965, 59, 435.
5. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 2320.

through the resin at a slow rate (2 drops per second), the amount (in ml) percolated being one third of the total exchange capacity of the resin. The clear solution of silicic acid, thus obtained, was again filtered through the sintered glass filter to make it free of suspended materials as far as practicable and stored in a Jena bottle. A portion of this silicic acid was analysed and found free of sodium. Thus the solution of silicic acid prepared was pure and its concentration was determined by heating a known volume to a constant weight as SiO_2 .

With a view to satisfying the requirements of the theory, the concentration of the sol used by us was so adjusted that its rate of polymerisation was very slow and finally it coagulated instead of forming a gel.

Shape of Silicic Acid Particles.—The shape of the particles of silicic acid is known from the observations of different authors⁵⁻⁸ who used electron microscope and light-scattering method. Light of wave length $546 \mu\mu$ was used by us. The intensity of the scattered light was measured at different angles in a cylindrical (one side frosted) cell and the process was repeated at suitable intervals. The intensities for these angles were then subjected to volume correction of the cell in the same way as reported in another communication⁶. It is found that the ratios, calculated from the theoretical curve for sphere⁹ for the angles used according to the equation

$$P_{\theta} = [3/x^3 (\sin x - x \cos x)]^2 \quad (1)$$

where P_{θ} is the particle scattering factor^{11,12} and $x = 4\pi/\lambda' \sin \theta/2$. $D/2$ (λ' = wave length of light in solution and D , the diameter of sphere) agree satisfactorily with the observed ratios. This is evident from curves 1, 2, and 3 of Fig. 1, in which the ratio P_{θ}/P_{90} has been plotted against x .

Determination of Turbidity and Particle Size.—The well-known equation due to Debye¹² has been used for the calculation of the turbidity:

$$T = (32 \pi^3/3)(\nu^2 n^2/\lambda^4)(1/N) MC \quad (2)$$

where n , ν ($= \delta n/\delta c$), C , M , and N represent the refractive index of the solvent, increment in the refractive index due to presence of solute in the solvent, the concentration of the solute in g./ml, the molecular weight of the solute, and the Avogadro number respectively.

The increase in turbidity with time of three sols containing 0.720%, 0.624%, and 0.702% of SiO_2 was measured. The turbidity was measured according to the direction given in the literature supplied with the Brice Phoenix Instrument. In all turbidity measurements the dissymmetry was always measured. From this dissymmetry values and the theo-

6. Radezewski and Richter, *Kolloid Z.*, 1941 **96**, 1.
7. Alexander and Iler, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1953 **57**, 932.
8. Shapiro and Kolthoff, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950 **72**, 76.
9. Doty and Steiner, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1950, **18**, 1211.
10. Lord Rayleigh, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1925, **A84**, 25.
11. Gans, *Ann. Physik*, 1925, **7629**.
12. *J. Phys. Coll. Chem.*, 1947, **51**, 18.

retical curve for sphere⁹, the correction factors were found out and used for evaluation of the correct turbidity from the observed data. The increase of corrected turbidity and dissymmetry with time have been shown in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3 respectively. From the theoretical curve for sphere⁹ and the dissymmetry values obtained at different times, the values of D/λ' , and hence the diameter of the particles, have been found out. These are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Time.	Diameter D (in $m\mu$).		
	% $\text{SiO}_2=0.702$. Temp.=30°.	% $\text{SiO}_2=0.624$. Temp.=31°.	% $\text{SiO}_2=0.720$ Temp.=30°.
48 hr.	..	55	..
52	73	..	..
72	91	96	..
93	..	..	118
96	122	124	..
116	..	..	168
118	..	153	..
120	149	..	..
139	..	174	180
144	178	..	..
161	..	..	192
168	190	182	..
185	..	..	198
190	..	195	..
193	195	..	..
211	..	..	202
239	..	196	..
286	..	197	..

Measurement of Depolarisation.—For the measurement of depolarisation, a sol having SiO_2 concentration of 0.702% was used. By adopting the procedure described in the literature (referred to previously) the depolarisation factors, p_u and p_v , were measured at different times during the course of polymerisation of the sol. The value of p_h has been calculated from the equation of Krishnan¹³:

$$p_u = \frac{1 + (1/p_h)}{1 + (1/p_v)}.$$

The values of p_v and p_h are zero and those of p_u 's are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

Time.	% $\text{SiO}_2=0.702$. Temp.=30°.		Time.	p_u .
	p_u .			
8 hr.	0.0030		120 hr.	0.0150
24	0.0000		144	0.0280
48	0.0048		168	0.0400
72	0.0080		185	0.0500
96	0.0096		200	0.0640

Determination of Molecular Weight.—The equation of Debye¹²:

$$HC/T = 1/M + 2BC \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

where H and B are two constants, C , T , and M are concentration, turbidity, and molecular weight respectively, was used. A plot of HC/T against concentration (C) will yield a straight line whose intercept will provide $1/M$.

With the object of following the change in molecular weight with time of a pure sol containing 0.625% of SiO_2 , the turbidity, dissymmetry, and depolarisation were measured. To evaluate H , the refractive index increment was measured in the Brice Phoenix Differential Refractometer and a value of 0.0405 was obtained for this increment. From the stage when the particles had grown appreciable in size, the sol was diluted to different concentrations (five or more) and the scattering of light was measured at different angles for each of these dilutions. Since our measurements were meant mainly for particles of size exceeding $1/10$ to $1/15$ of the wave length of light used, application of correction of observed turbidity by the factor $1/P_{90}$, obtained from dissymmetry and the theoretical curve⁹, was adopted. Values of HC/T , thus corrected, are then plotted against C and from the intercept of the straight line on the ordinate, the value of the average molecular weight has been calculated. Fig. 4 represents this plot. From the stage at which the sol begins to show depolarisation, the molecular weight has been corrected for depolarisation by the Cabannes factor¹³ $(6-7 p_u)/(6+3p_u)$.

The values of intrinsic dissymmetry for the different particle sizes were determined at the stages at which the molecular weights were determined. The plot of $1/Z$ against C yields a straight line in each case and the reciprocal of the intercept provides the value of intrinsic dissymmetry $[Z]$. Curves 1-4 of Fig. 5 illustrate this. From the value of $[Z]$ and the theoretical curve⁹, the true diameter of the particles of the sol at different stages of polymerisation has been determined.

Molecular Weight from Viscosity Measurement.—At the last stage of polymerisation (192 hours), when the silicic acid particles had attained more or less a steady size, the molecular weight was also determined by viscosity measurement. The viscosity was measured at 25° using an Ostwald type viscometer in which the rate of clearance of 2 ml of water was 130 seconds. The sol was diluted to five different concentrations and the time of clearance of 2 ml of it at each of these dilutions was noted. The specific viscosity was calculated from the relation, $\eta_{sp} = (t - t_0)/t_0$, where t and t_0 = times taken by the sol and the solvent (water) respectively. The plot of η_{sp}/C against C , extrapolated to zero concentration, provides the value of the intrinsic viscosity $[\eta]$. The plot has not been shown, but the data used for this plot are recorded in Table III.

TABLE III

Temp. = 25°. Time = 192 hours. $[\eta]$ (from graph) = 0.55.
Density from Einstein's equation = 0.0454 g./ml.

Conc. of SiO_2 (g./100ml) (C).	η_{sp} .	η_{sp}/C .
0.524	0.29	0.55
0.262	0.14	0.54
0.143	0.08	0.57
0.213	0.11	0.52
0.100	0.06	0.58

From the value of the intrinsic viscosity and the well-known equation of Einstein, $[\eta]\rho = k = 0.025$, for rigid spheres, the value of ρ (the density of the particle) has been calculated (vide Table III). Having thus known the density of the particle, its molecular weight was calculated from the following relation, using the diameter of the particle as obtained from the light-scattering measurements. Thus

$$M = 4/3\pi r^3 \rho N \quad (4)$$

where M , r , and ρ are molecular weight, radius, and density of the particle respectively and N is the Avogadro number. The average radius of the particle being 102.5μ , the average molecular weight has been found to be 121×10^6 .

DISCUSSION

The increase in turbidity with time of a pure silicic acid solution has been attributed to the onward polymerisation of the acid molecules through the agencies of their

FIG 1

Lines represent theoretical curves and circles represent experimental points.

functional groups (OH groups). This is analogous to glycol-adipic acid condensation polymerisation reaction studied by Flory¹⁴. It has been shown¹⁵ recently that this polymerisation process is a reaction of the third order in which two OH groups of two silicic acid molecules react and a third OH group, either of one of the reacting molecules or of a third molecule, catalyses the reaction.

As has already been stated, the concentration of the sol has been so adjusted that its rate of

polymerisation is very slow. Hence error arising from the amount of polymerisation during one set of experiments is small and can be neglected. From Fig. 1 (curves 1-3) it is evident that the theoretical line, obtained by plotting P_θ/P_∞ (taking particles as spheres) against the value of θ (for different angles at which the intensities have been measured), coincides very nearly with the experimental points demonstrated in the curves by open and solid circles. The curves 1, 2, and 3 correspond to measurements at 118 hours, 168 hours, and 239 hours respectively after the preparation of the solution. This close coincidence of the theoretical line with the experimental points at different stages of the polymerisation process proves that the silicic acid particles are spherical and the shape does not change during polymerisation.

14. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.* 1939, **61**, 3334; 1941, **63**, 3083, 3091, 3096; 1940, **62**, 2261,

15. Ghosh and Moulik, this *Journal*, 1962, **39**, 801.

1. Ghosh and Pal, this *issue*, p. 603.

The turbidity and dissymmetry curves in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3, respectively, are more

FIG. 2

or less S-shaped. At first the turbidity or the dissymmetry increases slowly, then rapidly, and finally slowly again. From this observation it can be inferred that there is a time at which rapid reaction among the hydroxyl groups (functional groups) takes place and this continues for a short period. On both sides of this period, the process of polymerisation is slow. It may be mentioned here that the dissymmetry values shown in Fig. 3 are not intrinsic values, but that obtained at the specified concentrations of

the sol used. Hence the diameters of the particles shown in Table I are not true values, but are those obtained from the dissymmetry values mentioned above.

From the data on depolarisation, recorded in Table II, it is evident that at first the values of P_u , P_v , and P_h are all zero. After some time the value of P_u becomes positive and increases steadily, while those of P_v and P_h remain all along zero. From this observation the conclusion may be drawn that the silicic acid particles are at first isotropic ones and as time passes, these grow in size, but their isotropicity does not change. This has also been observed by Greenburg and Sinclair⁴. Subramiah¹ and Guruswamy² have, however, obtained high depolarisation at the beginning of the polymerisation process which with time decreased to low values. At first greatly anisotropic particles are formed, which with time acquire isotropic nature, is the explanation of their observation. This point of difference is worth noting and further work is necessary for its elucidation.

FIG. 3

In Fig. 4, curves 1-4, obtained by plotting $1/Z$ against C , have been utilised for the evaluation of intrinsic dissymmetry $[Z]$ (dissymmetry at zero concentration) from which the average true size of the particles corresponding to a particular stage of polymerisa-

tion has been determined. The value of the particles size (diameter), thus found out, are 161 m μ , 190 m μ , 196 m μ , and 260 m μ at 118 hours, 144 hours, 160 hours, and 192 hours respectively, after the preparation of the solution. In this connection the diameters of sol and gel particles, obtained by different authors adopting different methods, are worth mentioning. These are recorded in Table IV.

FIG. 4

TABLE IV

Authors.	Materials.	Diameter D (in m μ).		
		Electron micrography.	Light scattering.	Sp. surface area.
Radczewski & Richter ⁶	Sol from hydrolysis of SiCl_4	200	..	..
Alexander & Iler ⁷	Ludox & silicic acid by ion-exchange method (six sols)	10.5, 18.8, 21.1, 28.4, 35.2 & 59.2 respec- tively	17.5, 23.0, 30.0, 43.0, 53.0 & 66.0 respec- tively	14.7, 18.9, 21.8, 28.1, 32.5 & 40.0 res- pectively
Nauman & Debye ³	Sodium silicate and HCl	66.0	66.0	..
Greenburg & Sinclair ⁴	Sodium silicate and ammonium acetate	..	(150-174) maximum and 20 or nearly minimum	..
Shapiro & Kolthoff ⁸	Dried silica gel or aerogel	..	..	(3-6).

The values of molecular weight of the sol at different intervals of time, obtained from graphical extrapolation method (Fig. 5, curves 1-4), are 52×10^6 , 119×10^6 , 121×10^6 , and 125×10^6 at 118 hours, 144 hours, 160 hours, and 192 hours respectively. These molecular

weights have been corrected for depolarisation, wherever necessary, and the Cabannes factors for correction are 1.0000, 0.9385, 0.9185 and 0.9139 respectively at the above mentioned hours. At the last stage of polymerisation (192 hours), the molecular weight obtained from viscosity measurements is 121×10^6 . At this stage the molecular weight obtained from light scattering is 125×10^6 . Thus the agreement is quite good.

FIG. 5

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